

Notes

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Neutralized β -Phenyl Pyruvic Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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THE oxidation mechanisms involving α -ketoacids and various ions of transition metals¹⁻⁴ along with the halogenation reactions of α -keto acids⁵⁻⁶ have already been studied. The kinetics of the oxidation of some α -keto acids by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) have been reported in our earlier communications⁷⁻⁸. Oxidation of β -phenyl pyruvate ion has been studied in view of the interesting results obtained with glyoxylate and pyruvate ions.

Experimental

Reagents: Neutralized β -phenyl pyruvic acid (Fluka A.G.) was used. The details of other reagents have been mentioned in earlier communications^{7,8}.

Procedure: The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) was followed spectrophotometrically⁷. The reaction was initiated by adding requisite quantity of the substrate into the solution containing the oxidant and alkali (in uncatalyzed reaction) or the oxidant, carbonate-bicarbonate buffer and osmium(VIII) (in catalyzed reaction), all maintained at a constant temperature. The disappearance of oxidant follows first order kinetics in the case of the uncatalyzed reaction and zero order kinetics in the case of the catalyzed reactions. The rate of loss of oxidant was followed for at least 50% reduction of initial hexacyanoferrate(III). All experiments were performed at 33° and osmium (VIII) catalyzed oxidations were always carried out at osmium(VIII) concentration of $2.0 \times 10^{-6} M$ unless otherwise mentioned.

The equivalents of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion consumed per mole of substrate were 6.5 in both the cases of uncatalyzed and catalyzed oxidations. The products of oxidation were found to be a mixture of benzaldehyde and benzoic acid in both the cases. Benzaldehyde was identified by preparing its 2:4 D.N.P. derivative (m.p.=234-235°, lit m.p.=235°). The melting point of benzoic acid, after separation, was noted to be 121° (lit m.p.=121°).

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Results and Discussion

In some experiments the concentrations of the reducing substrate, hydroxyl ion and catalyst (where present) were kept constant but the concentrations of initial oxidant were varied. The average values of k_1 (k_1 =pseudo first order rate constant) are $(3.75 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-4} \text{ (sec}^{-1}\text{)}$ at [Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = $(1.0-7.0) \times 10^{-4} M$, [β -phenyl pyruvate] = $2.18 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[\text{OH}^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ whereas the values of k_0 (k_0 =zero order rate constant) for the catalyzed reaction are $(3.7 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-6} \text{ (mole lit}^{-1}\text{ sec}^{-1}\text{)}$ at [Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = $(1.95-5.0) \times 10^{-4} M$, [β -phenyl pyruvate] = $2.18 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[\text{H}^-] = 6.3 \times 10^{-2} M$. The values of k_1 and k_0 along

FIGURE 1: Plot of $1/k_0$ against $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ for the osmium (VIII) catalyzed oxidation.

with the quotients, $k_1/[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}]$ and $k_0/[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}]$ for the respective reactions are summarized in Table 1. The rates are found to be proportional to the initial concentration of the reducing substrate.

The effect of hydroxyl ion concentration on the initial rates was studied at constant reactants and

catalyst (where present) concentrations (Table 2).

TABLE-1 EFFECT OF VARYING [β-PHENYL PYRUVATE] ON k_1 AND k_0 OF UNCATALYZED AND CATALYZED REACTIONS RESPECTIVELY.

(a) $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.75 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$					
(b) $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 2.92 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 6.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$					
$[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}] \times 10^3 (\text{M})$	2.18	4.36	6.54	8.72	10.0
(a) $k_1 \times 10^4 (\text{sec}^{-1})$	2.76	4.98	7.67	10.5	12.5
$\frac{k_1}{[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}] \times 10}$ (lit mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	1.27	1.14	1.17	1.20	1.25
$[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}] \times 10^3 (\text{M})$	2.18	4.36	6.54	8.72	10.9
(b) $k_0 \times 10^9 (\text{mole lit}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$	3.887	7.31	11.5	14.6	18.2
$\frac{k_0}{[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}] \times 10^9 (\text{sec}^{-1})}$	1.78	1.68	1.76	1.67	1.67

TABLE-2 EFFECT OF HYDROXYL ION ON THE PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT OF UNCATALYZED REACTION.

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, $[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}] = 2.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$					
$[\text{OH}^-] \times 10^2 (\text{M})$	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
$k_1 \times 10^4 (\text{sec}^{-1})$	1.79	3.65	5.84	7.36	8.33
$\frac{k_1}{[\text{OH}^-] \times 10^2 (\text{lit mol}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})}$	3.58	3.65	3.89	3.68	3.33

The values of $k_1/[\text{OH}^-]$ in the uncatalyzed reaction indicate that the rate is directly proportional to the initial OH^- concentration, whereas in the latter case the values of $k_0/[\text{OH}^-]$ gradually decreases with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ and the plot of $1/k_0$ against $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ is linear making an intercept (Figure 1). The reaction is too slow to be studied in hydroxyl ion concentration of 10^{-2}M . At this lower concentration of alkali, the reaction takes place at measurable rate only in the presence of catalyst. It seems that the rate is directly proportional to osmium(VIII) concentrations upto $[\text{Os}(\text{VIII})] \leq 3.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$ and after that the increase in rate is not significant and has tendency to remain constant (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2: Plot of k_0 against $[\text{Osmium (VIII)}]$.

The values of k_2 ($k_2 = k_1/[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}]$) and k_1 ($k_1 = k_0/[\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}]$) for uncatalyzed and catalyzed oxidations respectively have been calculated at various temperatures. The values of k_2 have been calculated to be 2.20×10^{-2} , 3.8×10^{-3} , 7.0×10^{-2} and 17.6×10^{-2} (lit mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹) at 31.5, 36.0, 40.0 and 45.0° respectively whereas the values of k_1 have been found to be 1.6×10^{-5} , 2.80×10^{-5} and 4.05×10^{-5} (sec⁻¹) at 33, 40.9 and 45.8° respectively for the catalyzed reaction. The values of ΔH^\ddagger have been found to be 30.0 ± 3.5 and 13.3 ± 1.2 (k cal mole⁻¹) for the uncatalyzed and catalyzed reactions respectively. The corresponding values of ΔS^\ddagger are 31.9 ± 9.5 and -37.2 ± 3.0 (e.u.) respectively.

It is suggested that $\beta\text{-phenyl pyruvate}$ (S) combines reversibly with the oxidant to form a complex (X) which in turn reacts with hydroxyl ion to give a free radical (Y) and hexacyanoferrate(II). The reaction mixture gave a suspension on addition of acrylamide. The free radical further picks up hexacyanoferrate(III) to give initial products (P*) of oxidation.

Scheme 1

Applying steady state approximation in intermediate X and Y, we get equation (4)

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1'k_2[\text{S}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots (4)$$

The first order rate constant k_1 comes out to be

$$k_1 = \frac{2k_1'k_2[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots (5)$$

If $k_{-1} \gg k_2[\text{OH}^-]$ the equation (5) reduces to equation (6) which is consistent with the experimental findings.

$$k_1 = k[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-] \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{where, } k = \frac{2k_1'k_2}{k_{-1}}$$

It has earlier been mentioned^{10,11} that perosmate anion exists as HO_2O_6^- . It is likely, therefore, that the complex (X) is formed by the interaction of substrate (S) and HO_2O_6^- (designated by Os (VIII)). The complex (X) thus formed decomposes in the presence of OH^- to give initial products of oxidation (P*) and osmium (VI). The latter is finally oxidized by two molecules of hexacyanoferrate (III) regenerating osmium (VIII).

Scheme II

The rate of formation of the complex is zero at steady state and hence the concentration of complex

$$[X] = \frac{k_4[S][\text{Os(VIII)}]}{k_{-4} + k_5[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III) is

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_4k_5[S][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-4} + k_5[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

$$1/\left(-\frac{d[\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-}]}{dt}\right) = \frac{k_{-4}}{2k_4k_5[S][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{2k_4[S][\text{Os(VIII)}]} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

A plot $\frac{1}{\text{reaction velocity}}$ vs. $\frac{1}{[\text{OH}^-]}$ should give a straight line with a positive intercept at the Y-axis. Such a plot is shown in Figure 1 which justifies the validity of the rate equation (11). The observed stoichiometry of 6.5 can be explained by considering that steps (i) and (ii) take place to the extent of 80% and 20% respectively. (i) $\text{PhCH}_2\text{COCOO}^- + 6\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-} + 5\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{PhCHO} + 2\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{4-} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (ii) $\text{PhCH}_2\text{COCOO}^- + 8\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{3-} + 8\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{PhCOO}^- + 2\text{CO}_2 + 8\text{Fe(CN)}_6^{4-} + 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The possibility that enolization of β -phenyl pyruvate followed by the oxidation and subsequent rupture of C-C bond to give initially benzaldehyde and oxalic acid, cannot be totally ruled out. However, it has earlier been shown⁹ that oxalic acid is not completely oxidized to CO_2 under the condition at which the reaction is carried out. The absence of oxalic acid in the reaction mixture indicates that oxidation via enolization may not take place.

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Chemical Investigation of *Poeciloneuron indicum* Leaves

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POECLONEURON INDICUM Bedd. (N. O. Guttiferae), trade name *Ballagi* is a large tree found in Western Ghats from North Kanara to Travancore at an altitude of 300–1,200 m. The tree yields a good quality timber for heavy constructional work. The fruit, bark and root of the plant are reported^{2,3} to yield friedelin. As a long range programme of better utilization of plant resources, investigation with the leaves of *P. indicum* collected from Shimoga forests (Mysore state), has been carried out and the results recorded here.

The alcoholic extractive of the shade dried powdered leaves (2 kg) was successively extracted with *n*-hexane and ether. The hexane extract on keeping deposited an FeCl_3 positive dirty yellow powder (9 g) which on crystallisation (pyridine) furnished yellowish crystals, m.p. >350° (Found: C, 55.70; H, 2.82, Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_6\text{O}_8$: C, 55.62; H, 1.98%) and was identified as *ellagic acid* by positive Griesmeyer Reichelsche reaction, and direct Comparison (TLC, IR) with an authentic sample.

The dark green residue obtained from the filtrate of ellagic acid on subsequent purification was chromatographed over Al_2O_3 column.

The *n*-hexane eluents yielded a substance, m.p. 71° (80 mg) which was identified as *hentriacontane* (m. m.p.; IR).

The *n*-hexane-benzene (3:1) elution of the column gave an LB positive and TNM negative residue (1.2 g) which on repeated crystallisation from benzene furnished needles, m.p. 256–258°; $(\alpha)_D^{25}$ – 30°; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1709 cm^{-1} . It was identified (m.m.p., IR, TLC) as *friedelin* (Found: C, 84.45; H, 12.10. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.50; H, 11.70%).